

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

A.NAVOY'S GHAZALS TRANSLATION AND ANALYSE

Matkarimov S.

Scientific researcher, Urgench State University,
Urgench, Uzbekistan

Abstract

The article is devoted to the French translation of A. Navoi's gazelle, which begins "Meni men istagan uz sukhbatiga arjumand etmas" and "Jonga chun derman not erdi ulmakim kayfiyati" by Hamid Ismoilov and Jean-Pierre Balpa. The author studied the work of translators in this area and conducted a deep analysis of the translation of a ghazal, that is, an Eastern work translated into Western European languages.

Keywords: Navoi, gazelle, translation, tadpole, dictionary, literary criticism, western, eastern, languages.

Introduction

The value of the work of art to be translated is determined by its content, ideological qualities, educational and educational significance, artistic aesthetic features. Scientific research in the fields of foreign literature, comparative literature, theory and practice of translation has become one of the current topics. After all, it is impossible to enjoy the ocean of world literature without translation, which is a tool of communication and influence, and in turn, it is impossible to fill it with the achievements of our national literature. The translation of the literature of peoples belonging to other nations and languages has always caused various problems and complications for the translator. The translation of historicity and nationality in the original should not cause difficulties for the reader, and the original should not contradict the reader's belief. If we look at the history of Uzbek artistic translations, we can see that the translation of the works that reflect the issues of nationality, historicity, and color in one or another degree has been followed in different ways, and no strict standards have been developed in this regard until now. In particular, it is noticeable that nationalism and historicity are not clearly reflected in works translated into Uzbek from foreign literature, especially from French literature, at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. One of them is insufficient knowledge of the history, culture, religion, lifestyle and traditions of Western nations. But in today's translations, it can be felt that the content of the work is adapted to the original as much as possible. Such defects can also be found in translations of samples of Uzbek literature into foreign languages. In the works of Uzbek writers translated into European languages, not only nationalism and historicity are violated in many cases, but also there are cases of introducing images and metaphors into the work that do not understand the main idea of the original, but are interesting to the Western reader. Contemporary translation studies support the point of view that it is necessary to create a translation according to the original in any case. Based on the best practices of the world translation practice, reaching a consensus in this regard is a requirement of today.

Methods and materials

The translation of Navoi's ghazals into French definitely shows the French reader that our nation has a very rich literary heritage. Translated into French by Hamid Ismailov and Jean-Pierre Balp, published by ORPHEE/LA DIFFERENCE..(ALISHER NAVOI. GAZELS ET AUTRES POEMES)¹ Алишер Навоий "Ғазал ва бошқа поэмалари" нашридан ўрин олган "Мени мен истаган ўз суҳбатига аржуманд этмас", матлаъли ғазалини француз тилига таржимаси таҳлилини кўриб чиқамиз. Таржима қилинган бошқа барча ғазаллар каби бу ғазал ҳам тадбил қилиниб, француз тилига эркин таржима усулида ўгирилган. We will analyze the translation into French of Alisher Navoi's "Ghazal and Other Poems" edition of the ghazal "Мени мен истаган ўз суҳбатига аржуманд этмас", "You don't want me to talk to you". Like all other translated ghazals, this ghazal was adapted and translated into French in a free translation method.

46-бет *Бадойиъ ул-бидоя 1 том 266 ғазал*

Мени мен истаган ўз суҳбатига аржуманд этмас,

Мени истар кишини суҳбатин кўнглим писанд этмас.

Не баҳра топқамен ондинки, мендин истагай баҳра,

Чу улким, баҳрае ондин тиларман баҳраманд этмас.

Нетай хуру пари базминки, қатлим ё ҳаётимға
Аён ул захрчашм айлаб, ниҳон бу нўшханд этмас.²

L'homme dont je rêve ne mérite pas mes paroles et la parole

de celui qui me cherche, mon cœur ne peut pas ne pas ignorer.

Quel profit tirerais-je de lui qui ne trouve profit de moi ?

Quel est ce profit que j'attends de lui et qu'il ne peut me donner ?

Que dois-je faire au festin des houris et des péris si pour ma mort et ma vie ,

les premières ne laissent pas couler le poison de leurs

¹ ORPHEE/ LA DIFFERENCE (ALISHER NAVOI. GAZELS ET AUTRES POEMES)

² Alisher Navoiy. Mukammal asarlar to'plami. 20 jildli. 7-jild. -T.: Fan, 1991.

yeux, les secondees ne se cachent pas pour sourire?

La forme de la lune et du soleil ne me sert de rien si, de leurs beautés,

Elles ne déchirent pas mon âme en multiples morceaux,

ne recourent pas mon corps à force de piques.

J'ai besoin du cri de ces assassines à cheval

qui ne galopent que dans mon cœur en ruines.

Cœur de clochard céleste ne consomme pas le mensonge,

pour ta fin le ciel ne mettra à ton cou d'autre corde que celle de la mort.

Si, pour ne pas lancer de sort, cette femme au visage de

lune cache le feu de sa face,

ne donne pas, Navoi, à ce feu de simples d'autre aliment que celui de l'amour.

arjumand - dear, precious, honorable, worthy; Zahrchashm - eye, eye contact;

Researches and results

Noshkhand - beautiful smile, sweet laugh; chobushi - godman, palace official; kotilvash-killer-like, like a murderer; majnunshior-following the path of madness; samandar-tulpor,; a beautiful horse; tip of sarrishta-kalava; basis of work; belt-loop, belt, chain, band; words like sipand-isiriq were used.³

The word "arjumand" in the ghazal matlaa is not used in the modern Uzbek language, but the Uzbek reader understands this archaism in the sense of "must". L'homme dont je rêve ne mérite pas mes paroles et la parole

de celui qui me cherche, mon cœur ne peut pas ne pas ignorer.

In the dictionary, this word means dear, precious, honorable, worthy. The fact that the translator chose the most correct option and gave the French word "merit" made it very easy for the French reader to understand the meaning of the ghazal. The lexeme of zahrchashm in the sixth verse of the third stanza of the ghazal is also an archaism, and we can see that the translator (le poison de leurs yeux) is given by two words, just like in the Uzbek language. Que dois-je faire au festin des houris et des péris si pour ma mort et ma vie ,

les premières ne laissent pas couler le poison de leurs

yeux, les secondees ne se cachent pas pour sourire?

the lexeme noshkhand in this verse is also an old word, and the translator expressed it through the word (pour sourire) because it means to burst out laughing, to laugh openly. In the translation of the next verses of the ghazal, tadbil translation was used in the same way.

In-depth study of the history of translation is not only important for studying the general process of cultural development or the history of specific national literature, but also for determining the current development process, features, scope of literary relations of that literature, and determining the perspective of development. It is known that the recognition of values specific to the spirituality of a

nation by other nations is, of course, an expression of deep respect for the history of that nation. Such recognition serves to increase the pride and pride of the people, national identity. The possibilities of translation of literary works of any language are realized on the basis of literary traditions and rich experience gained in the field of translation for several decades.

The goal of each new translation and new work of art is to accept the best artistic monuments of other nations in their native language, to introduce them to the people, to creatively assimilate the best qualities of the culture of the brotherly nations, to translate the noteworthy works created in their literature into the language of other nations, and to present them to them. is a tool. The value of an artistic work being translated into the languages of other nations cannot be determined by the price or unit accepted in each country. The value of a work of art is determined by its content, that is, its ideological qualities, educational-educational significance, artistic-aesthetic properties.

The customs, cultures, and dreams of foreign countries often seem strange to us. Navoi's ghazal "Jong'a chun derman" is being analyzed

Jong'a chun derman: ne erdi olmakim kayfiyati?

They say that the reason is the intensity of the internal disease.

The lyrical hero of the ghazal is a lover. He came to the brink of death from the fire of love. That's why he asks his soul directly in the matla (beginning of the ghazal): "What is the reason for his death?" And John answers him: "It was caused by the severity of the disease in the body."

J'interroge mon âme: «Quelle est la source de ma mort?»

Elle répond: «De la puissance du mal dans ton corps.

Жисмдин сўрсамки, бу заъфингга не эрди сабаб?

Дер: анга бўлди сабаб ўтлуқ бағирнинг хирқати

In the second stanza, the lyrical hero turns to the body and asks: "What caused you to get into this situation?" And the body's answer is as follows: "It was caused by the squealing of the grass." J'interroge mon corps: «Quelle est la cause de ton mal?»

Il répond: «L'ardeur de ta flamme intérieure.»

Чун бағирдин сўрдим, айтур: андин ўт тушиди манга

Ким, кўнгулга шуъла солди ишқ барки офати.

In the third stanza, the question is asked to Baghir, and he answers: "My heart is burning, because the disaster of thirst for love has struck my heart." J'interroge ma flamme intérieure: elle répond que ce feu qui s'étend

n'est que reflet des brasiers de l'Amour en mon cœur.

Кўнглима қилма ғазаб, айтурки, кўздиндур гунаҳ ,

Кўрмайин ул тушмади бизга бу ишнинг тўхмати.

³ Navoiy asarlari tilining izohli lug'ati. II jild. -T.: Fan, 1983.

In the fourth stanza, logically, the lyrical hero "makes the heart angry", so he blames the sin on the eyes: "If the eyes had not seen, we would not have suffered the slander of this deed." Je m'empote contre mon cœur, il dit: « Tes yeux provoquent le péché, s'ils ne regardaient pas celui-ci ne pourrait te maudire.»

Кўзга чун дерманки, эй тардомани юзи қаро,
Сендин ўлмиш телба кўнглимнинг балою ваҳшати.

In the fifth stanza, the lover now "takes" the eye: "O black face with a wet skirt, the trouble and terror of my heart is from you." Je dit à mes yeux : «Mécréants à la face noire douleur

et sauvagerie de mon cœur fou viennent de vous. »

Йиғлаб айтур кўзки, йўқ эрди манга ҳам ихтиёр,

Ким, кўринди ногоҳон ул шўхи маҳваш талъати.

In the sixth stanza, the eye's crying answer is given: "I had no choice either, what should I do if suddenly the ul-shokhi mahvash (moon) talat was seen?" Pleurant, ils repondent : « Lorsque le feu solaire de ce visage à beauté de lune

s'impose à nous nous n'avons plus de volonté.»

Эй Навоий, барча ўз узрин деди, ўлгунча куй

Ким, санга ишқ ўти- ўқ эрмиш азалининг қисмати.

Coming to the eulogy (the last stanza of the ghazal), the lyrical hero turns to the poet and says: "O Navoi, everyone has apologized, sing until you die, because love is your eternal destiny.

"Ecoute Navoi, tous se trouvent des excuses, enflamme –toi à mort :

le feu de l'Amour est pour toi seul la dernière des fleches de l'éternité.

Tardoman - corrupt, shameless; Weakness - weakness; illness; tal'at- image; mahvash-like a moon⁴

Conclusion

It is necessary to find the equivalent of modern Uzbek words and translate them correctly, because if such lexicons are not given modern meanings, the meaning of the entire ghazal may change. Therefore, when translating historical works, the translator should make a special dictionary of obsolete words in the work and give their meanings today, if this is not possible, he should explain them through annotations. It will be important to the world literature as a masterpiece from Uzbek literature. Having taken from the sample of this article, not only East literature fonder, but also West fonders can be motivated from this literature. It will be first analyses from Old Uzbek hand scripts translated without any linking words.

We should analyze such kind of materials much more than as usual. In conclusion, we can say East Middle literature can illustrate the healthy life style, culture and science can be easily understandable to the European readers and can be integration to in the world literature.

References

1. Sotimov. U. Study of Alisher Navoi's life and work in Western European oriental studies. Dr. Dissertation, Moscow, 1988.
2. Sotimov. U. Navoi i Zapad. Tashkent. Izdatel'stvo "FAN" Academic Republic of Uzbekistan.
3. M. Kholbekov "Uzbek literature in France" edition of "Fan". Tashkent 1988.
4. M. Hakimov. "Lyrics of Alisher Navoi and folk oral creativity" "Fan" publishing house. Tashkent 1976.
5. Z. Gofforova. "Idea of a perfect man in Navoi's ghazals" Turon zamin ziya publishing house-Tashkent 2016

⁴ Navoiy asarlari tilining izohli lug'ati. III jild. -T.: Fan, 1984.